

Urban Air Mobility Operations: Evaluating Exposure to Lightning Strikes

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Abstract— The escalating demand for innovative modes of commuting within sprawling urban conglomerations has spurred the necessity for new transportation services. Predominantly utilizing electric Vertical Takeoff and Landing (eVTOL) technology, Urban Air Mobility (UAM) envisages operations at lower altitudes and speeds, facilitating connectivity between vertiports across cities or acting as shuttles linking various points within airports. UAM is subjected to rigorous regulatory scrutiny, reflecting the innovative characteristics inherent in its design. An important concern in regulatory considerations is the effect of the atmospheric electric environment on UAM operations. Notably, the eVTOL requires a lightweight design to meet operational viability, constrained by the weight limitations imposed by its electric motors. Using primarily composite materials for its construction results in a lighter structure, albeit offering a distinct level of lightning protection compared to metallic structures. Given the multiple challenges and complexities inherent in its operation, understanding the electrical environment where the eVTOL will operate in cities is of great value. In urban areas, aerosols and heat islands enhance lightning activity by intensifying the severity of thunderstorms. Therefore, the trajectory of UAM flights will require navigating around cumulonimbus clouds and associated convective structures, which pose a significant risk of lightning incidence and strong wind gusts. Based on these considerations, this work investigates how urban atmospheric environments affect the operation of eVTOLs by analyzing lightning strike probabilities in dense cityscapes. Through a literature review and theoretical frameworks, the study examines the regulatory landscape, technological constraints, and environmental characteristics to assess this critical aspect of UAM safety and contribute to the ongoing discussion on UAM, specifically concerning lightning exposure and possible strategies to mitigate incidents and/or accidents.

Keywords— UAM, eVTOL, lightning, urban electrical environment, aircraft design

I. OBJECTIVE AND MOTIVATION

The objective of this paper is to investigate the impact of the urban atmospheric environment on UAM operations, specifically focusing on the probability of lightning strikes

and their effects on eVTOL. This study aims to analyze the challenges posed by enhanced lightning activity in urban areas, to assess the current technological landscape by understanding these critical factors. The results intend to contribute to the operational safety of UAM in densely populated cities.

II. BACKGROUND

UAM represents a transformative approach to urban transportation, focusing on using low-altitude airspace to alleviate congestion and improve connectivity in densely populated areas. UAM takes advantage of recent technological advancements to create a network of eVTOL aircraft. These new eVTOL air taxis are expected to be safer, quieter, and less expensive to operate and maintain than traditional helicopters. UAM integrates into multimodal transportation systems, offering safe, secure, and sustainable air transportation for passengers and cargo. The vehicles can be remotely piloted or have a pilot on board, and their operations are envisioned to significantly enhance urban travel by providing efficient, real-time connectivity via information-enabled platforms such as ride-hailing apps [1]. Reference [1] is a comprehensive review that meta-analysed about 800 articles about UAM, electrical ground vehicles (EV) and autonomous ground vehicles (AV) that were published from January 2015 to June 2020.

The introduction of eVTOL aircraft marks a significant advancement in aviation technology. These aircraft are characterized by their ability to take off, hover, and land vertically, much like a helicopter, but with the operational efficiency and environmental benefits of electric propulsion. eVTOL aircraft are powered by advanced battery systems and utilize distributed electric propulsion, which involves multiple electric motors distributed across the airframe. This design enhances safety through redundancy, as the failure of a single motor is less likely to compromise the entire vehicle. Furthermore, eVTOLs are expected to be quieter, more energy-efficient, and cheaper to operate and maintain compared to traditional aircraft [1].

The development and deployment of eVTOLs are driven by significant advancements in battery technology, autonomy, and materials science. These aircraft primarily use composite materials, which are lighter than traditional metal structures but pose unique challenges in terms of lightning protection and structural integrity [2]. While challenges like limited battery energy density and infrastructure requirements exist, ongoing research and development efforts are continuously improving eVTOL capabilities, making them a promising solution for the future of air transportation [3]. Figure 1 shows some of the most promising UAM currently in development.

The eVTOL industry is actively exploring various configurations to optimize aircraft performance and adaptability to different operational scenarios. These configurations include multi-rotor, compound, tiltrotor (wing), and tail-sitter designs, each with its own advantages and disadvantages depending on the intended use case [4]. For instance, multi-rotor eVTOLs are well-suited for short to medium-range missions due to their simple design and maneuverability, while compound and tiltrotor configurations excel in longer-range operations due to their enhanced aerodynamic efficiency at higher speeds [4]. The tail-sitter configuration, with its unique ability to transition between vertical and horizontal flight modes, is particularly suitable for logistics and cargo operations [4].

Fig. 1 Different UAM aircraft design, Wisk (2024), EVE (2024), AIRBUS (2024), LILIJUM (2024)

UAM vehicles are designed to operate from dedicated hubs known as vertiports, which can be strategically placed on rooftops, vacant land, or existing infrastructure such as airports and helipads. The integration of these vertiports into the urban environment is critical for the effective deployment and scalability of UAM services. Key factors in determining vertiport locations include population density, potential travel time savings, airspace restrictions, and safety considerations, particularly regarding lightning strikes [1].

Table I shows the data retrieved from EVE about the time comparison between a journey by car vs one using eVTOL, the time saving, and the zero CO₂ emissions makes the use of this alternative very attractive [5].

The urban atmospheric environment presents distinct challenges for UAM. Studies indicate that urban areas experience more frequent lightning compared to rural areas, largely due to the urban heat island effect, which intensifies convective activity, and the increased concentration of

aerosols from pollution. These factors can lead to more frequent and severe thunderstorms, thereby increasing the lightning activity [6-8].

TABLE I
SAVED TIME COMPARISONS FOR A JOURNEY BY CAR VERSUS ONE USING
EVTOL

Route	Time UAM	Time Car
Miami, from International Airport to South Beach	15 min	45 min
Singapore, from Nagoya Hill to Marina Bay	9 min	45 min
Sydney, from Sydney Airport to Sydney CBC	6 min	50 min
South Africa, from Johannesburg to Pretoria	19 min	90 min

The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) is actively developing regulations and guidelines to ensure the safe integration of UAM operations, their initial draft contains the concerns regarding lightning protection for eVTOL aircraft. The draft advisory circular referenced in [9], shows that UAM aircraft must be "protected against catastrophic effects from lightning". The development of these kinds of regulations underscores the FAA's commitment to establishing stringent safety standards for UAM operations, recognizing the unique vulnerabilities of eVTOL aircraft to lightning strikes due to their low-altitude flight profiles and reliance on electrical systems [9].

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper adopts a methodology to assess the lightning strike risk to eVTOL aircraft in urban environments. The approach integrates a review of existing literature and analysis of historical lightning strike data. The analysis may also investigate other meteorological variables, such as temperature, humidity, winds, and instability indexes.

A review of existing literature was conducted to gather information on lightning, the interaction of lightning with aircraft, and the unique characteristics of the urban atmospheric environment. This review will encompass peer-reviewed articles in aerospace engineering, meteorology, and electrical engineering, as well as technical reports and white papers.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The increased cloud-to-ground (CG) lightning activity over urban areas observed in [6, 10] underscores the elevated exposure UAM operations face in these environments. The study found that the CG flash density over the Sao Paulo Metropolitan Area (SPMA) was 150-200% higher than in surrounding areas. The reference [10] observed a similar phenomenon in South Korea, where negative flash density increased by 40-64% and positive flash density increased by 26-49% over urban areas compared to their surroundings. This increase was attributed to the urban heat island effect and the elevated concentration of aerosols due to pollution. These factors can intensify convective activity and influence cloud

electrification processes, leading to a higher frequency of lightning strikes.

The elevated concentration of cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) in urban environments, resulting from anthropogenic emissions of particulate matter and secondary gases, significantly alters the microphysics of clouds. The abundance of CCN leads to a higher number of smaller cloud droplets, which hinders the coalescence process that typically forms raindrops. Consequently, this increases the liquid water content in the mixed-phase region of the cloud, where supercooled water droplets and ice coexist. The higher liquid water content in this region enhances charge separation, leading to a higher frequency of lightning strikes [11]. This study suggests that urban thunderstorms are generally more intense, producing more lightning flashes per storm compared to rural counterparts. This intensification is linked to the urban heat island effect, which can lead to stronger updrafts and more vigorous cloud development. Consequently, these thunderstorms are not only more frequent but also more electrically active.

Moreover, the type of lightning produced in urban areas may also be influenced by the urban environment. The reference [6] showed an increase in CG flash density over large cities around 60-100% and a potential decrease in the percentage of positive CG lightning flashes in urban areas compared to rural areas. This shift in lightning polarity might be attributed to the increased concentration of pollutants in the atmosphere, which can affect the electrification processes of the clouds. While the exact mechanisms are still under investigation, it underscores the complex interplay between urban environments and lightning activity. This increased lightning strike risk makes the urban environment more complex to operate an UAM.

The findings of [12] further support the link between increased aerosol concentrations and lightning activity. Their study over three air-polluted urban areas in China revealed that CG lightning density was higher under conditions with high aerosol optical depth (AOD), a measure of aerosol concentration. This suggests that aerosols can invigorate thunderstorms and lightning production by affecting cloud microphysical processes.

The implications of this increased lightning risk are significant for UAM operations. eVTOL aircraft, with their low-altitude flight profiles and reliance on electrical systems, are particularly vulnerable to lightning strikes [2]. A single strike can cause both direct and indirect effects, potentially leading to catastrophic consequences.

The impact of lightning strikes on aircraft can be categorized into direct and indirect effects [14]. Direct effects involve physical damage to the aircraft structure and components, while indirect effects pertain to the description or damage of electrical systems due to induced electromagnetic fields [15]. While conventional aircraft have historically relied on mechanical and pneumatic systems, the shift towards more-electric aircraft (MEA) and all-electric aircraft architectures increases the susceptibility to electromagnetic interference (EMI) and induced currents from lightning [15].

Given the reliance of eVTOL aircraft on electrical systems for propulsion and control, the risk of indirect effects is a significant concern for UAM. The characteristics of UAM aircraft and associated lightning effects are summarized in Table II presented in the study from [2].

TABLE II
CHARACTERISTICS OF UAM AIRCRAFT AND ASSOCIATED LIGHTNING EFFECTS

Characteristics	Problems	Lightning Effects
composite materials	low electrical conductivity	high structural damage
low velocity	lightning dwell time	
low altitude	exposure to urban environment	exposure to cloud-to-ground discharge
urban flight		
small size	low magnetic permeability	low electromagnetic shielding effect
large windshield		
electric engine	high electromagnetic sensitivity	high electromagnetic interference effect
avionics		

The probability of a lightning strike to an aircraft is estimated to be approximately one strike in every 10,000 flight hours. A region where it is prone to lightning estimated the average probability of a lightning strike every 1000 flight hours. Therefore, the probability lies between one strike per 1,000 and 20,000 flight hours according to [13].

To comply with these regulations, eVTOL manufacturers are expected to incorporate robust lightning protection measures into the design and construction of their aircraft. This includes the integration of lightning protection systems, such as diverter strips and grounding points, to redirect lightning currents and minimize damage. Additionally, the FAA mandates that electrical and electronic systems critical for the continued safe flight and landing of the aircraft must be designed to withstand lightning exposure and recover normal operation promptly. These regulatory measures aim to ensure that eVTOL aircraft can operate safely in various weather conditions, including those with lightning risks, thereby fostering public confidence in the emerging UAM industry [9].

Given the unique design and operational characteristics of eVTOL aircraft, their vulnerability to lightning strikes requires special consideration. The reference [2] highlights that eVTOL aircraft, due to their small size and low-altitude flight profiles (typically 0.5-1.5 km), are more likely to encounter CG lightning. Figure 2 shows an aircraft being struck by lightning just after takeoff, it clearly shows a full lightning channel [16].

The relatively slow speeds of eVTOL aircraft, compared to conventional airplanes, can increase the dwell time of a lightning strike on the aircraft. This prolonged exposure potentially heightens the severity of damage from lightning

strikes compared to conventional aircraft. While the magnitude of damage at the lightning attachment site may be similar, the relatively smaller size of eVTOL aircraft intensifies the overall impact [2].

Fig. 2 Lightning striking an airplane near the Vancouver airport at low altitude just after takeoff.

The successful integration of UAM into urban environments depends not only on aircraft design and technology but also on addressing operational challenges. There is the need for robust fleet management systems, including autonomous flight capabilities, remote operation centers (ROCs), and efficient airspace management strategies [17].

To ensure safe operation of eVTOL aircraft in urban environments, several lightning protection measures need to be considered: component placement, shielding and grounding, material selection, and testing and certification. Placing components in less vulnerable zones mitigates the risk of lightning strikes but may necessitate longer wiring and additional structural support, increasing the aircraft's overall weight. Effective shielding and grounding are essential to protect electronic systems from Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) and High Intensity Radiated Fields (HIRF), yet these systems can substantially add to the aircraft's weight, which is critical for battery efficiency and flight range. Lightweight design is essential for optimal battery performance [18].

To mitigate the lightning risk, several strategies can be implemented. One approach is to adjust UAM flight paths and schedules to avoid areas with high lightning activity, especially during peak hours. This can be achieved by utilizing real-time weather data and lightning detection systems to identify and avoid thunderstorms. Additionally, implementing robust lightning protection measures in the design and construction of eVTOL aircraft is crucial. This includes incorporating lightning protection systems, to redirect lightning currents and minimize damage.

Furthermore, the development of advanced lightning detection and warning systems specifically tailored for UAM operations can provide early warnings to pilots and operators, allowing them to take evasive actions or seek shelter. The integration of advanced lightning warning systems, as discussed by [19], should be considered for UAM operations. These systems, utilizing technologies such as electric field mills and lightning detection networks, can provide real-time

warnings of approaching thunderstorms and potential lightning strikes. By incorporating these warnings into flight planning and operational procedures, UAM operators can make informed decisions to avoid hazardous weather conditions, enhancing the overall safety and reliability of UAM operations in urban environments.

Reference [20] shows that the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing real-time weather monitoring and prediction. The use of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and IoT to analyze sensor data is useful for identifying patterns for accurate forecasting. This research where AI-enabled IoT systems utilize neural networks to process environmental data from various sensors, providing real-time weather updates and predictions to mitigate lightning strike risks. These advancements underscore the growing importance of AI and IoT in enhancing the accuracy and accessibility of weather information, which could be used as an alternative to have a better prediction of lightning risk during the UAM operations.

Reference [21] sets guidelines for safely launching spacecraft in various weather conditions, focusing particularly on lightning. Although this standard is meant for spacecraft, it can provide valuable insights for eVTOL aircraft safety. The ambiguities it refers to involve situations where it's unclear which specific criterion should apply to a given weather scenario, such as when multiple criteria related to clouds, lightning, and electric fields could be relevant. In such cases, the standard advises applying all potentially relevant criteria to ensure safety. This includes assessing cloud formations that are physically connected as a single entity to evaluate lightning risk comprehensively. While reference [21] isn't directly applicable to eVTOLs, adapting its guidelines could benefit UAM operations. The standard emphasizes a conservative approach to safety, which is particularly important for eVTOLs operating in complex urban environments where cloud formations can be diverse and unpredictable. Furthermore, it mandates the use of all necessary weather monitoring equipment and procedures to ensure compliance with the criteria. This could imply that UAM stakeholders might need to invest in sophisticated weather monitoring systems and develop rigorous operational procedures to align with a future standard for eVTOL operation. For instance, the standard's requirement for a 30-minute waiting period after lightning occurrences within 10 nautical miles of the flight path could necessitate real-time lightning detection capabilities and protocols for flight path adjustments or delays.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The increased CG lightning activity in urban areas poses a significant challenge to UAM operations. The findings of [6] highlight the need for a multi-faceted approach to mitigate the lightning risk. This could include adjusting flight paths and schedules, implementing robust lightning protection measures in eVTOL aircraft, and developing advanced lightning detection and warning systems. By addressing these challenges, the safety and reliability of UAM operations in

urban environments can be significantly enhanced. The discussions are still under development within an ongoing study and the results will be available in future publication. Within the same study, a further review will address characteristics of lightning channel and its specificities within urban environments.

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